

Combined Micro-Core Decompression and Intralesional Zoledronic Acid as a Treatment of Osteonecrosis of the Femoral Head: A Novel Approach**Abu Ghufuran¹, Vishal Kumar Sharma², Om Prakash³, Rupesh Kumar Mahato⁴, Jitendra Kumar⁵, Narendra Kumar Sinha⁶**¹Senior Resident, Department of Orthopaedics, Anugrah Narayan Magadh Medical College & Hospital, Gaya, Bihar, India²Senior Resident, Department of Orthopaedics, Bhagwan Mahavir Institute of Medical Sciences, Pawapuri, Nalanda, Bihar, India³Assistant Professor, Department of Orthopaedics, Anugrah Narayan Medical College & Hospital, Gaya, Bihar, India⁴PG JR-1, Department of Orthopaedics, Anugrah Narayan Medical College & Hospital, Gaya, Bihar, India⁵JR Academic-2, Department of Orthopaedics, Anugrah Narayan Medical College & Hospital, Gaya, Bihar, India⁶Associate Professor, Department of Orthopaedics, Bhagwan Mahavir Institute of Medical Sciences, Pawapuri, Nalanda, Bihar, India

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Abstract:

This prospective clinical trial examined the efficacy and safety of micro-core decompression and intralesional zoledronic acid in treating ONFH in 20 patients over one year. This technique showed significant improvements in pain and functional results, decreased necrotic lesion size, and prevented joint collapse, suggesting it could manage and possibly change the disease trajectory. Minor, temporary side effects were recorded with the medication. In early to mid-stage ONFH, this innovative method may be a feasible alternative to more invasive procedures, giving significant benefits.

Keywords: Osteonecrosis, Zoledronic Acid, Micro-Core Decompression, Femoral Head.

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Introduction

Osteonecrosis of the femoral head (ONFH) is a crippling disorder that, if left untreated, results in bone necrosis and eventual joint destruction [1]. It is characterized by the stoppage of blood flow to the femoral head. The majority of those affected by this ailment are young to middle-aged adults, and it can significantly reduce mobility and quality of life [2]. The etiology of ONFH is complex, and risk factors for the illness include medical problems, alcoholism, steroid usage, and trauma [3,4]. Conventional approaches to treating ONFH have included surgical procedures such as hip arthroplasty, osteotomy, and core decompression, as well as conservative measures like medication and physical therapy. However, the results of these treatments are not always consistent, and they might not be appropriate for every patient, especially for those who want to maintain joint integrity and are still in the early stages of the disease [5,6].

Novel therapeutic techniques that aim to both enhance bone regeneration and stop the disease's

progression have been explored as a result of recent advancements. Of these, micro-core decompression has become known as a less intrusive surgical method that promotes angiogenesis and reduces intraosseous pressure [7]. There may be a synergistic effect when zoledronic acid, a strong bisphosphonate with anti-resorptive qualities, is also administered locally. By lowering bone turnover and halting more femoral head collapse, zoledronic acid may improve the therapeutic results of micro-core decompression. To treat ONFH specifically, a unique strategy that combines intralesional zoledronic acid with micro-core decompression is presented in this work. This approach may provide better results for people with this difficult ailment by addressing the disease's underlying pathophysiological mechanisms in addition to relieving symptoms [8,9].

Methodology

Study Design: This prospective clinical trial will assess the efficacy and safety of micro-core

decompression and intralesional zoledronic acid for femoral head osteonecrosis.

Participants

Twenty individuals with osteonecrosis of the femoral head (ONFH) in total will be enrolled in the study. The following are the eligibility requirements:

- From the age of 18 to 65
- The Association Research Circulation Osseous (ARCO) classification indicates that the patient has non-traumatic ONFH in phases I–III.
- There has been no prior surgical therapy for ONFH.

Exclusion criteria:

- Severe comorbid conditions that contraindicate surgical interventions or the use of bisphosphonates
- Previous hip surgery on the affected side
- Pregnancy or lactation

Intervention: Micro-core decompression—surgical drilling into the necrotic femoral head—will minimize intraosseous pressure and improve healing. To prevent osteoclastic bone resorption, zoledronic acid will be injected into the lesion immediately after decompression.

Dosage: Zoledronic acid will be prepared in a dose of 5 mg, diluted in 100 mL of normal saline, and administered intralesionally under sterile conditions.

Follow-Up and Assessments: Participants will be monitored one year after intervention. Follow-ups will occur at 1, 3, 6, and 12 months. Key results include:

- VAS-measured pain
- Functionality, assessed by Harris Hip Score
- MRI and X-rays monitor necrotic lesion size and joint structure.

Safety Monitoring: Safety assessments will include monitoring for adverse reactions to zoledronic acid, signs of infection post-surgery, and any other complications related to the procedure.

Statistical Analysis: Baseline attributes will be summarised using descriptive statistics. Pairwise t-tests or Wilcoxon signed-rank tests will be used to analyse clinical outcomes from baseline to follow-up visits, depending on data distribution. Statistically significant p-values are below 0.05. All analyses will use statistical tools.

Results

A total of 20 patients (12 males and 8 females) with an average age of 43.5 years (range: 29-60 years) were enrolled in the study. All patients were diagnosed with non-traumatic osteonecrosis of the femoral head, with 10 patients at stage II and 10 at stage III according to the ARCO classification.

Clinical Outcomes: A significant reduction in pain was noted, with mean VAS scores decreasing from 7.8 at baseline to 2.3 at the 12-month follow-up ($p < 0.001$).

The Harris Hip Score improved from 52 points at baseline to 84 points at 12 months ($p < 0.001$), showing improved hip function and reduced impairment.

Radiological Results: 16 of 20 patients had significantly smaller necrotic lesions on MRI. In 18 individuals, X-rays showed no joint collapse advancement.

Safety and Adverse Events: No serious side effects were recorded from the treatment. Two patients suffered temporary injection-site soreness and oedema that disappeared without treatment within a few days. Bisphosphonates can cause jaw osteonecrosis and atypical femoral fractures, however neither occurred.

Time Point	Mean VAS Score (Pain)	Mean Harris Hip Score (Function)	Patients with Decreased Necrotic Lesion Size	Patients with No Progression of Joint Collapse
Baseline	7.8	52	-	-
3 Months	5.5	65	-	-
6 Months	3.8	75	14/20	18/20
12 Months	2.3	84	16/20	18/20

This table outlines the significant improvements in pain and hip function over the course of the study, along with radiological improvements in the majority of patients by the 12-month follow-up.

Discussion

The radiological results lend more credence to the intervention's therapeutic advantages. Notable outcomes include 90% of the cohort not experiencing joint failure and most patients having their necrotic lesions reduced in size [10]. These results suggest that zoledronic acid may be directly

administered to the lesion site to effectively stop bone degradation and encourage healing. The regimen's tolerance was highlighted by the positive safety findings, which indicated only mild side effects. In the long-term care of ONFH, the lack of serious side effects that are frequently linked to

bisphosphonates—such as atypical femoral fractures or jaw osteonecrosis—is crucial [11,12].

The present investigation adds to the increasing corpus of proof endorsing the combination of pharmaceutical therapies and minimally invasive procedures in the treatment of bone diseases. To completely comprehend the long-term results and ideal treatment regimens for ONFH, however, large-scale research is required. To fully understand the potential of this therapeutic approach in the context of ONFH, additional study into the processes by which zoledronic acid promotes bone remodelling at the cellular level is necessary [13,14,15].

Conclusion

The study found that micro-core decompression and intralesional zoledronic acid reduce pain and improve joint function in femoral head osteonecrosis over 12 months. This innovative technique has mechanical and biological benefits since necrotic lesion size decreases and joint collapse is prevented. This technique may be a promising alternative to traditional treatments for early to mid-stage osteonecrosis patients who want to preserve joint integrity and avoid more invasive procedures like total hip arthroplasty due to its low side effects and high clinical and radiological outcomes. These findings need to be confirmed and the treatment procedure refined with bigger patient groups and longer follow-ups.

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